

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

IMPROVING NEONATAL PROCEDURAL PAIN MANAGEMENT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Lauren Flowers

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Penny Weismuller, Dr.PH., R.N., Project Chair
Dana Rutledge, Ph.D., R.N., Committee Member

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ABSTRACT

Neonates experience repeated routine painful procedures during the course of hospitalization and often times this is done with no measure of pain relief. Although nurses are aware of hospital guidelines and policies and procedures for alleviating neonatal pain, adherence with documentation of pain assessments and reassessments remains low. In March, 2014, a neonatal pain audit was conducted to assess nurse's compliance with neonatal pain management in a Maternal/Neonatal Unit in a large Southern California Magnet® hospital. Audit revealed a lack of documented neonatal pain scores and post pain assessments. To improve documentation of neonatal pain; collaboration with Information Technology (IT) Department was accomplished to integrate a computer based build using the electronic health system and nursing educational interventions. The computer integration build makes it difficult for nurses to fail to document pain assessment before and after painful procedures. An alert is built into the system to remind nurses to document a pain assessment at the start of painful procedures as well as post procedure/intervention. The procedural pain computer integration education involves use of IT-created pictorial representations of how to document from beginning to end. Planned evaluation includes assessment of workability, nurse's knowledge of procedural pain management, and audits procedural pain management documentation.

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BACKGROUND

Neonates experience numerous routine diagnostic procedures moments after a hospital birth and during the course of hospitalization. Repeated painful procedures may lead to maladaptive pain response such as hyperalgesia, a negative consequence noted in neonates who have sustained greater than 5 or more painful procedures during the first 24 hours of life (Taddio, Shah, Atenafu, & Katz, 2009). These painful procedures are often done with no measure of pain relief (Weissman, Aranovitch, Sharaga, & Zimmer, 2009). The most common painful procedure experienced by neonates is heel lancing and the subsequent squeezing of the heel to obtain a blood specimen, which causes increased pain, and potential damage to the surrounding tissues (Morrow, Hidlinger, & Wilkinson-Faulk, 2010).

Historically, neonates were believed to be incapable of pain perception due to immature central nervous systems. However, findings from neurobiologists corroborate that neonates experienced pain through neurodevelopmental characteristics of nociception (Weissman et al., 2009). Neonates manifest nociception as behavioral and physiological responses to noxious stimuli. Furthermore, after painful procedures, neonates have increased sensitivity to pain, experiencing pain more intensely (Asadi-Noghabi, Tavassoli-Farahi, Yousefi, & Sadeghi, 2014), and demonstrating persistent levels of altered behavior (Cong et al., 2013).

According to Twycross and Collins (2013), newborns exhibit both behavioral and physiological changes in relation to pain and stressful situations, and make an effort to remove harmful stimuli. Behavioral indices include changes in facial expression, gross motor body movements, and crying. Physiological indices of pain in newborns include

variations in blood pressure, heart rate, respirations, and oxygen levels (Weissman et al., 2009). Untreated or unrelieved pain in neonates may pose harmful consequences later in life (Cong, Delaney, & Vazquez, 2013; Twycross & Collins, 2013). Therefore, caregivers should evaluate neonatal pain surrounding procedures using validated pain assessment tools and follow up high pain levels with appropriate pain management strategies (Walter-Nicolet, Annequin, Biran, Mitanchez, & Tourniaire, 2010).

In 2001, standards in assessment, management, and reassessment of pain in hospitalized patients were revised and implemented (The Joint Commission on Accreditation of Healthcare Organizations, 2012). Even though these mandates have been widely disseminated as an important quality metric in patient care, breakdowns in pain management processes continue to occur. Therefore gaps concerning provider pain knowledge, evidence, and practice must be addressed (Cong et al., 2013) as these breakdowns translate into unnecessary pain and suffering especially in the care of vulnerable populations such as neonates. Assessment, management, and evaluation of pain protocols should be in place on all units that care for newborns and performed in accordance with hospital guidelines and policies and procedures. Reliable pain assessments should be completed in a systematic manner (Gradin & Eriksson, 2010) before and after an actual or potential painful procedure to assess, quantify, and evaluate a newborn's pain in order to provide the best interventional approach for treatment (Walter-Nicolet et al., 2010; Weissman et al., 2009).

Changing nurses' behaviors by translating best evidence into clinical practice is essential to supporting positive patient outcomes (Costa et al., 2009). The use of audit and feedback as a strategy to bring awareness to nurse's clinical practice is an important

intervention when reinforcing their performance with established clinical guidelines (Ivers et al., 2013). Adequate and frequent feedback is essential in order to ensure that the change in clinical behavior is addressed in a timely manner and gives feedback recipients time to adjust behavior to that which is acceptable under established clinical guidelines. The use of information technologies may also be beneficial in changing nurses' behaviors surrounding documentation adherence through the use of computer-based prompts and on-screen reminders (Farmers et al., 2011). Reminders at the point of care are important because they pop up automatically on-screen while the nurse is documenting in real time in the electronic health record (EHR). The reminder gives information to the nurse to document a specific element of care that may have been inadvertently omitted if the prompt was not available thereby ensuring that proper documentation of procedures takes place (Cheung et al., 2012).

Statement of the Problem

In clinical areas where care is delivered to newborns, untreated or unrelieved pain exists (Cong et al., 2013). One reason for this is that many nurses may believe neonates do not experience pain or do not have the capacity to recollect painful stimuli due to immature nervous systems (Akuma & Jordan, 2012). In fact, even very premature neonates exhibit the neural capability to respond to noxious stimuli; evidence supports that neonates experience pain (Asadi-Noghabi et al., 2014). Therefore, improvement of assessment and treatment of procedural pain is important and the use of pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions can be used to minimize pain and suffering.

Although many nurses are aware of hospital guidelines and policies and procedures for alleviating neonatal pain, adherence remains low. Gaps exist in nurses'

knowledge of neonatal pain, consequences of unrelieved pain, and neonatal pain management. Often, nurses' own personal and unsubstantiated beliefs about newborn pain may interfere with their responsibility to manage neonatal pain effectively (Akuma & Jordan, 2012; Lavanya, Vatsa, & Lodha, 2013).

Another problem related to neonatal pain assessment is lack of documentation of assessments and interventions surrounding painful neonatal procedures. Lack of documentation has complex etiology but it is possible that lack of prompts for documentation impedes nurses from documenting.

Local Problem with Neonatal Pain

In March, 2014, a neonatal pain audit was conducted by Maternal/Newborn Unit pain management champions in a large Southern California Magnet® hospital. The reason for the audit was to assess nurse's compliance with neonatal pain management policies and procedures. More specific to this project, the audit confirmed whether nurses were making the following documentations:

- Pain assessments that included a score on the Neonatal Infant Pain Score (NIPS) when a procedure had the potential to cause pain and/or tissue damage.
- Pain intervention(s) used before and after such procedures.
- Neonate response to pain intervention (effective or ineffective?).

Audit results indicated that many nurses did not document neonatal pain scores surrounding painful procedures nor did they reassess pain following pain management interventions which is required by hospital policies and procedures. Interventions include swaddling, holding, feeding, audio distraction, tactile distraction, pacifier, sucrose

pacifier, repositioning, facilitated tuck, blanket roll, analgesia, and other. Personnel involved in the audit concluded that there was a lack of documentation in NIPS scoring painful procedures and a lack of documentation of neonatal pain after pain management interventions.

Improving nursing documentation when assessing neonatal pain surrounding a painful procedure is equally as important as doing the pain assessments and measures need to be taken to address this. Currently, there are no processes in the hospital electronic medical record (EHR) to prompt nurses to perform a pre and post pain assessment surrounding a painful procedure. Collaboration with the Information's Technology (IT) department in the hospital to create an interventional build into the EHR to prompt nurses to document pain assessments will be integral to ensuring that documentation of neonatal pain occurs.

Purpose

The purpose of this doctoral project, a performance improvement initiative, will involve developing a test of change focused on neonatal pain management in a maternal/newborn unit. The innovation developed for this project has three components: (a) working with IT to create a computer pain module upgrade in the EHR to remind/prompt nurses to complete a pre and post pain assessment; (b) procedural pain computer integration in-services; and (c) development of a plan for evaluation of neonatal pain documentation once nurses have received the program and the IT change has occurred.

When completed by all nurses on the unit, it is hoped that the interventional change in documentation process with reminders/prompts and appropriate instruction on

this will do the following: (a) provide standardization for documenting neonatal pain scores pre and post painful procedure; (b) reduce barriers to pain assessment/management and its documentation; and (c) improve nursing compliance with hospital pain management policies and procedures. The ultimate outcome is reduction in unnecessary pain and suffering experienced by newborns.

Supporting Framework

The framework used in this project is the Plan Do Study Act (PDSA) model for quality improvement developed in 1939 by Edwards-Deming (Langley, Nolan, Nolan, Norman, & Provost, 2009). The model for PDSA quality improvement consists of four cycles:

- Plan, employs the scientific method to develop a theory for improvement;
- Do, a systematic method for data collection;
- Study, examination and interpretation of findings; and
- Act, the implementation of the step-by-step process to arrive at a desired outcome.

The PDSA model is a hypothesis that originates from theory (Epstein et al., 2011).

Using PDSA model for quality improvement will determine if the information in the multimodal intervention aimed at neonatal pain documentation demonstrates a positive change in neonatal procedural pain scoring by nurses (Epstein et al., 2011). The PDSA model allows nurses to conduct a test of change, gather supporting data to demonstrate change was effective, evaluate what worked and did not work, and to re-test the model again if necessary. Because the model is cyclical in nature, it offers continuous re-evaluation of the implemented change and provides the flexibility to

review the model to assure the guidelines are suitably translated into clinical practice (see Figure 1; Langley et al., 2009). As a cyclical model, PDSA is a systematic process that allows nurses to embark, guide, take ownership, and thereby affect the success of the change. The success and sustainability of the process change is mainly dependent on staff buy-in and letting go of old ways of doing things in order for the change to prevail.

Figure 1. The Model for Improvement (Langley et al., 2009, p. 24).

LITERATURE REVIEW

For this project, evidence is sought that focuses on newborns undergoing procedures and their pain assessment/management, as well as nurse barriers to neonatal pain assessment/management, changing nurses behaviors in managing neonatal pain, and utilizing information technology to change nurses documentation behaviors. Evidenced-based sources written in English were reviewed after it was determined that they were appropriate to the project. Search of CINAHL, Google Scholar, and Pub Med were conducted using the key search terms “neonatal,” “pain,” “procedural pain,” “assessment,” “nurse barriers,” “PDSA,” “model for quality improvement,” “changing behaviors,” “improving documentation,” “audit and feedback,” “prompts,” “clinical decision support,” and “technology in nursing education .”

The search was effective in finding many relevant articles in neonatal pain management, changing nurses’ behaviors, and changing documentation behaviors. Reference lists of the available primary studies were also evaluated to determine if there were any additional relevant citations. Studies were analyzed if their focus appeared relevant on the basis of title, and abstract. Evidence used for this literature synthesis can be viewed in the Table of Evidence (see Appendix A, Tables 1, 2, 3, and 4).

Assessing and Managing Procedural Pain in Neonates

Despite the growing body of evidence concerning assessing and managing procedural pain in newborns, development of validated pain assessment instruments, and hospital policies regarding documentation, neonatal pain continues to be unrecognized, undertreated, and not documented (Akuma & Jordan, 2012; Cong et al., 2013; Pölkki et al., 2010; Walter-Nicolet et al., 2010). Assessment of neonatal pain is difficult especially

because neonates are unable to verbalize their pain (Cong et al., 2013; Gradin & Eriksson, 2010; Pölkki et al., 2013; Walter-Nicolet et al., 2010). For this reason, the onus for assessing and managing neonatal pain becomes the responsibility of healthcare providers. Nurses as primary providers of neonatal care are responsible for recognizing and managing neonatal pain effectively (Byrd et al., 2009; Cong et al., 2013; Gradin & Eriksson, 2010).

According to Gradin and Eriksson (2010), effective pain management begins with a reliable and systematic pain assessment to enhance awareness for the need to alleviate and treat pain. Cong et al. (2013) cited several studies in which nurses were asked about their pain assessment practices. The results of these studies validated low use of valid and reliable scales: California nurses verbalized that although they often use pain assessment tools, they worried about their accuracy, and relied upon their personal instincts to assess neonatal pain; the majority of Finnish nurses assessing neonatal pain did so without pain scores; nurses in the United Kingdom and Australia reported low use of pain assessment scales.

Byrd, Gonzales, and Parsons (2009) demonstrated inconsistencies between nurses knowledge, beliefs regarding neonatal procedural pain, and integrating knowledge into practice. They mailed a survey to 300 National Association of Neonatal Nurses (NANN) members in California to identify barriers to neonatal pain management and got a 30% response rate. Although nurses acknowledged neonates experience more pain than other patient populations, only 45% of nurses agreed that neonatal pain was adequately managed, 44% agreed they received sufficient training during orientation, and 55% stated they had received ongoing neonatal pain management education.

In a comparison of nurses from the United States and China, Cong et al. (2013) examined neonatal nurse's perception of neonatal pain. Findings revealed US nurses, 65% reported using pain scales to measure neonatal pain while Chinese nurses only used them 43% of the time. A primary barrier to optimal pain management identified by American nurses was resistance to change; while Chinese nurses cited inadequate staffing and time constraints. In order to improve the care of neonates, nurses need to recognize that neonatal procedural pain occurs and should be assessed, comprehend what pain management barriers exist, and work to address these barriers in order to bridge the gap between knowledge and practice (Pölkki et al., 2010). Improving nursing knowledge and changing nurse's behaviors concerning neonatal pain is essential (Twycross & Collins, 2013).

Gradin and Eriksson (2010) conducted a prospective study in Sweden in which the use of neonatal pain assessment was surveyed across a 15-year period beginning in 1993. Findings demonstrated a gradual rise in the use of pain assessment scales: 2% in 1993, 19% 1998, 23% 2003, and 2008 = 48%. Even though the numbers are encouraging, the 2008 data indicated that much work needs to be done to increase the use of pain assessments. Often times, the healthcare providers' own personal beliefs about pain may interfere with pain assessment and management (Asadi-Noghabi et al., 2014; Lavanya et al., 2009). In these cases, educational strategies need to be implemented in order to expand nurse's knowledge, use of pain assessment tools, and multimodal approaches for managing pain (Asadi-Noghabi, et al., 2014; Lavanya et al., 2009).

During the initial hours and days of life, neonates experience many painful procedures in which their pain may be untreated (Walter-Nicolet et al., 2010;

Weissman et al., 2009). Unrelieved or untreated pain has the capacity to cause behavioral and physiological changes due to juxtaposition of areas in the brain that process emotion, pain perception, and thought processes (Akuma & Jordan, 2011; Pölkki et al., 2010). In fact, newborns exposed to multiple (5 or more) painful procedures during the first day of life demonstrate a higher altered pain response or hyperalgesia when compared to neonates that had fewer needle sticks (Morrow et al., 2010; Taddio et al., 2009). These changes may lead to lasting increased pain sensitivity or pain sensitization later in life (Morrow et al., 2010; Taddio et al., 2009; Walter-Nicolet et al., 2010; Weissman et al., 2009).

Continuous and persistent unrelieved pain in the neonatal period produces unfavorable biological and biochemical changes to the developing structures in the neonatal brain that trigger over activation of immature neurons that induce stress (Pölkki et al., 2010). These changes predispose neonates to long term cognitive and neurodevelopmental changes well beyond the neonatal period (Akuma & Jordan, 2011; Asadi-Noghabi, et al., 2014; Cong et al., 2013; Pölkki et al., 2010). As cited in Cong et al. (2013), an increased number of needle punctures is significantly correlated to a reduction in white and subcortical gray matter development, decreased body weight, and a smaller head circumference.

Since it may not be feasible to avoid painful procedures altogether in neonates, there are several pain-reducing effective methods for the treatment of procedural pain. These include pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions, or a combination of both. Pharmacological interventions used for the treatment of procedural pain include opioids, non-opioids, local anesthesia, and analgesia. Opioids have been used for the

treatment of procedural pain in neonates but due to possible harmful side effects, risk of tolerance, and dependency, they are only recommended for short term use (Walter-Nicolet et al., 2010). Non-opioid analgesics have been shown to be efficacious for the treatment of mild to moderate continuous neonatal pain due to low risk of side effects, various methods of administration, and safety; however, they have been proven ineffective for relieving heel lancing pain (Walter-Nicolet et al., 2010).

Eutectic Mixture of Local Anesthesia (EMLA), a local anesthetic and injectable lidocaine, has been successfully used for treatment of more invasive procedures such as lumbar puncture and circumcision (Lavanya et al., 2009). No evidence was found for its use in the treatment of heel lancing pain. Pharmacological interventions, although effective for procedures, are not an effective method for the treatment of heel lance pain. Therefore, non-pharmacological interventions or a combination of the two need to be incorporated to ameliorate the effects of procedural pain due to heel lancing (Walter-Nicolet et al., 2010).

Several non-pharmacological pain interventions have proven effective in assuaging mild to moderate pain in neonates (Asadi-Noghabi et al., 2014; Walter-Nicolet et al., 2010). These methods can be used both pre and post-procedure. They include breastfeeding, facilitated tuck, positioning, kangaroo care, non-nutritive suck with and without sucrose, skin-to-skin contact, and swaddling (Morrow et al., 2010; Walter-Nicolet et al., 2010; Weissman et al., 2009). Non-pharmacological interventions are economical, tolerated well by newborns, may be used alone or as a complement to pharmacological interventions, and have been shown to decrease pain in newborns

(Walter-Nicolet et al., 2010; Weissman et al., 2009). Evidence for this literature synthesis can be viewed in Appendix A, table 1 of table of evidence.

Barriers to Managing Procedural Pain

Pain, a complex and multidimensional phenomenon when coupled with a patient population that cannot verbalize pain and suffering, becomes the responsibility of the caregiver (Byrd et al., 2009; Cong et al., 2013; Gradin & Ericksson, 2010). For this reason it is essential for nurses to understand their own personal beliefs, knowledge, and attitudes surrounding neonatal pain as they can be barriers to the delivery of quality care (Byrd et al., 2013; Czarnecki et al., 2011). A nurse's own personal values and beliefs are strong predictors for not utilizing pain interventions for the treatment and alleviation of pain as the endurance of "pain" can be viewed as character building (Asadi-Noghabi et al., 2014; Lavanya et al., 2009; Twycross & Collins, 2013).

The most common reasons given by nurses for not treating procedural pain in neonates is the belief that newborns do not have the ability to feel pain due to immature central nervous systems and do not recollect painful experiences (Akuma & Jordan, 2011; Byrd et al., 2009; Cong et al., 2013; Lavanya et al., 2009). Nurses mistakenly believe that neonatal brains were not fully developed to recollect painful experiences (Walter-Nicolet et al., 2010; Weissman et al., 2009). This latter myth has been disproven by scientific evidence that suggests that even premature neonates have the neural aptitude to respond to noxious stimuli and experience pain (Asadi-Noghabi et al., 2014; Byrd et al., 2009; Cong et al., 2013).

Gaps exist concerning neonatal pain knowledge, evidence, and practice (Akuma & Jordan, 2011; Cong et al., 2013). Some nurses and physicians lack sufficient

knowledge to assess the degree of pain experienced by neonates, the competence to effectively use pharmacological, and non-pharmacological methods when a procedure was identified as having the ability to produce minor to severe pain (Akuma & Jordan, 2011; Asadi-Noghabi et al., 2014; Cong et al., 2013; Lavanya et al., 2009). In fact both nurses and physicians report that although neonates experience pain and undergo numerous painful procedures for routine care, they rarely used interventions to treat their pain (Akuma & Jordan., 2011; Asadi-Noghabi et al., 2014; Cong et al., 2013). This demonstrates that while evidence supports the use of pain relieving interventions, inconsistencies exist in the application of these interventions and barriers for managing procedural pain continue due to insufficient pain management education (Akuma & Jordan, 2011; Asadi-Noghabi et al., 2014; Byrd et al., 2009; Czarnecki et al., 2014; Lavanya et al., 2009; Twycross & Collins, 2013). For example, when nurses were surveyed about receiving pain management education during job orientation, 44% agreed they had received adequate training (Byrd et al., 2009), and 47% of U.S. nurses and 56% of Chinese nurses agreed (Cong et al., 2013), 55% agreed their unit offered ongoing newborn pain management (Byrd et al., 2009). Details about these studies can be found in Appendix A, Table 2 in the Table of Evidence.

Changing Nurse Behaviors

Translating research into clinical practice has been a challenging endeavor (Costa, Cecatti, Milanez, Souza, & Gulmezoglu, 2009; Squires et al., 2009). In order to drive positive change and modify nurse's behaviors to adopt change, nurses need to feel a sense of ownership and care about the proposed change (Costa et al., 2009). More importantly, they need to feel they have a voice in decisions surrounding the change

(Epstein et al., 2011). In order to facilitate change and change nurse's behaviors, no single intervention is best at modifying clinician behaviors. Audit and feedback (AF), is a strategy used to enhance clinical practice by prompting healthcare providers to modify their practice when provided with feedback about inconsistencies in their clinical performance and established guidelines (Costa et al., 2009; Ivers et al., 2012; Ivers et al., 2014). Audit and feedback, a cyclical model begins with assessment of existing clinical practice and standards of care set into practice (Costa et al., 2009; Ivers et al., 2012). These standards are monitored, analyzed, applied, reassessed, and modified again as needed. The cycle of AF continues until sufficient behavioral change has been achieved (Costa et al., 2009).

Costa et al. (2009) conducted a systematic review of 11 studies in which AF strategies were examined to determine if behavior change would occur. The authors determined that while AF was effective in modifying clinician behaviors, rigorous feedback was an essential driver in changing behaviors and adopting new evidence into clinical practice. Ivers et al. (2012), suggested that AF may be an effective strategy in changing behaviors when clinicians were given Audit and feedback results of their performance measured against that of their peers and clinical guidelines (Costa et al., 2009; Ivers et al., 2014). The assumption behind this strategy is that if clinicians feel they are performing below set clinical standards they will be motivated to perform at the same level if not higher than their peers after receipt of AF.

Ivers et al. (2012) conducted a systematic review to examine the effects of AF in improving clinical practice and to determine factors that contribute to the effectiveness of AF use. The authors reviewed studies that provided education for improvement with

feedback structured as a set goal or action plan, verbal and written feedback, feedback given by a supervisor, and frequency of feedback (Ivers et al., 2014). They determined that although AF leads to small improvements in clinical practice they were significant enough to cause an overall improvement in healthcare providers compliance with desired outcome measures when AF was used correctly, given by a supervisor, and delivered on a regular basis in both verbal and written form with clear goals and action plans (Ivers et al., 2014).

Printed educational materials (PEMs) are a strategy used to increase provider knowledge, abilities, practice, patient outcomes, and are the most frequently used educational method for distributing information to healthcare providers (Farmer et al., 2011; Ivers et al., 2012; Ivers et al., 2014). Printed educational materials offer a small yet positive bearing in modifying organizational culture and provider behavior(s) in clinical practice when AF was given on provider performance through use of passive distribution of educational materials in comparison to no interventions (Ivers et al., 2012; Ivers et al., 2014). Therefore, the use of PEMs as a strategy for modifying provider behaviors along with AF may be a viable factor. Printed educational materials are a familiar source to providers for acquiring information, and are user friendly, cost effective, convenient to use, and lead to positive healthcare improvements (Farmers et al., 2011, Ivers et al., 2012; Ivers et al., 2014).

In an attempt to improve the health and safety of patients, healthcare organizations spend a considerable amount of time and money in quality improvement measures to enhance the knowledge and skills of its healthcare providers (Forsetlund et al., 2009). One way in which organizations attempt to achieve this outcome is by

offering educational meetings/programs to providers to enhance knowledge and modify behavior change in clinical practice. These educational meetings include conferences, courses, lectures, seminars, symposiums, workshops, and interactive workshops in which AF and/or PEMs are components. Educational meetings can play a role in improving provider practice and healthcare outcomes (Forsetlund et al., 2009). Although the effect may be small and comparable to other types of interventions such as AF, PEMs, and prompts, they were considered significant enough to cause behavior change in providers (Cheung et al., 2012; Farmer et al., 2011; Ivers et al., 2012; Ivers et al., 2014; Squires et al., 2014).

In a systematic review to appraise the efficiency of multimodal interventions in contrast to single component intervention in changing healthcare provider's behaviors in clinical practice, Squires et al. (2014) found mixed findings on whether single or multimodal interventions were equally effective at modifying provider behaviors. Multimodal interventions when compared to single component interventions require more resources, capital, complex to deliver, and sustain. Healthcare organizations need to do a cost assessment in order to ascertain if multimodal interventions are a better alternative to single component interventions at modifying healthcare provider's behaviors as there was no clear evidence that multimodal interventions are more effective than single component interventions at modifying behaviors (Forsetlund et al., 2009; Squires et al., 2014). Details about these studies can be found in Appendix A, Table 3 in Table of Evidence.

Utilization and Integration of Informatics to Change Documentation Behaviors

The utilization and integration of informatics to change nurse behaviors is a relatively new concept that may be used to alter nurse behaviors surrounding documentation adherence, (Cheung et al., 2012; Evenson & Mensch, 2013) and may help to close the gaps that continue to exist between research and recommended best clinical practice (Costa et al., 2009; Squires et al., 2009; Shojania et al., 2009). Best practices of clinical decision support (CDS) are electronic interventions such as reminders, prompts, or best practice advisory alerts (BPAs) which appear on the computer screen when the provider clicks on an encounter. The BPA alert appears in a new smaller window with a bright yellow banner which contains pertinent best practice information. Computer decision support systems BPA alerts serve a two-fold purpose. They are geared at modifying provider behaviors as long as the alert is given at the appropriate time and record when the BPA alert fired, the providers' name, and whether the provider accepted, canceled, or overrode the alert, which can later be used as an audit report tool to monitor for compliance (Evenson & Mensch, 2013; Klatt & Hopp, 2012; Lurio et al., 2010).

Therefore, such interventions must be delivered at the point of care to remind healthcare providers to document information they could forget while performing patient care related activities. This intervention when used appropriately may help to improve patient care delivery, safety, and increase documentation compliance in clinical practice (Cheung et al., 2012; Evenson & Mensch, 2013; Ivers et al., 2012; Ivers et al., 2014; Phansalkar et al., 2013). Computer-based prompts may also be a positive strategy for quality improvement initiatives but should be used appropriately and in moderation as overuse may lead to alert fatigue (Evenson & Mensch, 2013; Klatt & Hopp, 2012; Phansalkar et al., 2013). Alert fatigue is the "mental state resulting from receiving too

many alerts that consume time and mental energy, which can cause important alerts to be ignored along with clinically unimportant ones” (Phansalkar et al., 2013, p. 489). Also, this may cause providers to override the alert to move on with documentation (Klatt & Hopp, 2012; Phansalkar et al., 2013). Therefore, strategies must be considered to avoid alert fatigue such as only employing a single alert at a time or using hard stops for very important information. Hard stop alerts force providers to address the alert because they cannot be overridden without provider documentation. Best practice soft stop alerts may also be used, but they do not force providers, to document allowing the providers to ignore or override the alert if they so choose (Klatt & Hopp, 2012; Lurio et al., 2010).

In a systematic review of the effectiveness of on-screen computer prompts and reminders on process and outcomes at the point of care, Shojania et al. (2009) found a small to moderate improvement on increasing provider documentation. A larger improvement was noted with reminders and prompts that required end users to input a reply in order to continue. In general, computer-based reminders and prompts delivered at the point of care have demonstrated small to moderate improvements in modifying provider behaviors in documentation unless they required the user to input a response.

Cheung et al. (2012) systematically reviewed studies that gauged the effectiveness of computerized prompts in modifying provider behaviors in clinical practice. The intervention was a reminder or prompt that appeared on the computer screen to remind the healthcare provider to either write a prescription or order a test. The authors concluded that reminders had a positive impact on changing healthcare provider behavior in documentation and improving processes of care at the bedside. More specifically, computer technologies that required a response were more effective in changing

professional behaviors. In general, computer generated reminders provided a positive impact on clinical practice, are reasonably inexpensive, and easy to disseminate in many clinical settings provided that they are used in moderation and at the point of care (Cheung et al., 2012; Lurio et al., 2012; Phansalkar et al., 2013; Shojania et al., 2009). Details about these studies can be found in Appendix A, Table 4 in the Table of Evidence.

METHODS

This quality improvement project with an aim at changing pain documentation behaviors in maternal/neonatal nurses was conducted on a maternal/newborn unit in a large Southern California magnet hospital using PDSA model for quality improvement.

Sample/Setting

The target of the behavior change is staff nurses on a maternal/newborn 60-bed unit of a magnet-designated hospital in Southern California. Licensed vocational nurses will be excluded from this educational program as they do not assess neonatal pain. The total number of maternal/newborn nurses is 145.

Timeline

The following timeline outlines the implementation process for the computer integration build and educational intervention.

November, 2014. Assistant nurse manager presented the procedural pain computer integration build at the Clinical Services Informatics and Technology Team (CSITT). CSITT approved proposal for build.

April, 2015. The IT department is scheduled to create the neonatal procedural pain computer integration build approved for build, IT department to create the neonatal procedural pain computer integration build. The build consists of adding a bedside procedure group to the newborn assessment flow sheet above the NIPS pain scale group and attaching a Best Practice Advisory (BPA) to the procedure type row in the newborn surgical log flow sheet to remind staff to complete pain scores.

May, 2015. IT will create job aid (Appendix A) and in-service education for the staff on the use of the new electronic documentation fields will be given by the assistant nurse manager.

June, 2015. Full integration of IT builds into the EHR is anticipated. All RNs will be sent the educational materials and the in-service calendar via email. Assistant nurse manager and unit pain management champions and author begin the educational intervention in-services (see Appendix C).

July, 2015. Best Practice Advisory (BPA) audits and workbench audit reports will be conducted one month after the educational intervention in-services have taken place. Best Practice Advisory (BPA) audits will be conducted by the assistant nurse manager and pain management champions on individual electronic health records. The audit will record every time a BPA fired during the hospital encounter by date, time, and user name. Workbench audit reports will be run electronically by the assistant nurse manager. The audit will record patient location, date/time NIPS score was documented, pain intervention documentation, and user name. This will allow the assistant nurse manager to customize the audits thereby allowing for immediate shift feedback to staff for improved documentation compliance. Audits will be run monthly to demonstrate if the educational intervention in-services made an impact on documentation compliance. Any noted increased procedural pain documentation will be noted as positive as this was never documented before this educational intervention was given.

Ethical Considerations

For this quality improvement (QI) project, ethical procedures being used for implementing an evidence-based newborn pain management educational program for

nurses and reporting data from electronic audits done regularly on a maternal/newborn unit. There is no known risk to patients with this QI project, and minimal risk for nurses participating in the educational program. With her position as Assistant Nurse Manager, this doctoral student has access to the specific audit data and will be working with nurses on her unit to improve patient care. Quality improvement is an essential part of clinical practice and, is held to the ethical standards used to guide patient care (Lynn et al., 2007); when generalizable knowledge is not sought, minimal risks are involved, and processes of care are based upon the best knowledge available, quality improvement processes are ethical.

RESULTS

Intervention

This project will involve a change in the electronic health record (EHR) documentation of newborn procedural pain. The assistant nurse manager will work directly with the IT department to develop a “build” in the EHR that will add a bedside procedure group to the newborn assessment flow sheet above the NIPS pain scale group. This currently does not exist and the goal by placing the NIPS under to bedside procedure group is to remind nurses to document a NIPS pain score by the strategic placement under the bedside row. The EHR change will also involve attaching a BPA to the procedure type row in the newborn surgical log flow sheet to remind staff to complete pain scores. The BPA will automatically be delivered when the nurse clicks on the newborn surgical log flow sheet. The BPA will alert the nurse to document a pain assessment (at the start of procedure) and post procedure/intervention (30 minutes after procedure/intervention completed). In order for the BPA to go away, the nurse needs to accept the BPA and continue with documentation.

The procedural pain computer integration in-services will involve use of Information Technology (IT) created job aid(s) that are pictorial representations of how to document the new EHR computer integration build from beginning to end. All educational materials will emailed to all RNs one month prior to the in-services taking place by assistant nurse manager. The email will contain the job aid (Appendix B), power point presentation (Appendix C) that will provide brief education on procedural pain management importance, NIPS pain scoring, and pre-intervention build and post-intervention build.

The assistant nurse manager and unit pain management champions will provide group and one-on-one educational in-services to all unit RNs. Following the education, nurses will have to demonstrate understanding and competence in how to use the new IT integrations in the newborn EHR, and demonstrate steps to perform a NIPs score pre and post bedside procedure.

Specific computer-based BPA builds will be appended to the EHR, including the following additions:

1. Bedside procedure group (which previously did not exist) to the existing newborn assessment flow chart. More specifically, the bedside procedure group when clicked by the nurse for the purpose of documenting a bedside procedure (heel stick, veni-puncture, injection) will open a drop down cascade that will allow the nurse to document the specific bedside procedure performed (prior to this build there was no place for a nurse to document a bedside procedure). This build will be placed above the NIPS pain scale group in the EHR as a visual reminder to complete the newborn pain score.
2. Attach a Clinical Decision Support (CDS) BPA, which is a best clinical practice guideline for screening or treatment to reduce unnecessary variation and improve quality in the clinical setting. The BPA will be a soft stop and will be added to the procedure type row in the newborn surgical log flow sheet as a reminder to RNs to complete pain scores. This will be activated or fired when the nurse clicks on the procedure type row. The BPA documentation alert that will read as follows: “Complete pain score documentation for procedure (at start of procedure) and post procedure/intervention (30 minutes

after procedure/intervention completed).” Since this is not a hard stop, it will not force the nurse to document a response. As a soft stop, the nurse will have to either accept or cancel the BPA but will not be able to override and close the BPA. As a built in process, the system will be able to record the date and time in which the alert fired and the nurse that fired the alert as well as recording if the nurse accepted or canceled the alert for report notification and compliance. Along with the BPA computer integration build the IT department will create a job aid(s) for use by pain management champions to in-service nurses on these processes.

3. The IT department will create a CDS BPA audit report and workbench reports. The BPA audit report will provide information on when the BPA alert was fired, by whom it was fired, and date and time the alert was fired. Also, a workbench report will be created that will capture patient location, patient name, date/time range of NIPS, pain intervention, and user placing documentation for the neonatal pain documentation audit. These audit reports will be run by the assistant nurse manager on a daily, weekly, or monthly basis to ensure staff compliance with the educational interventions.

Once the BPA computer integration build has been created by IT, along with the job aid(s), the assistant nurse manager will create a power point presentation that gives a brief introduction to procedural newborn pain, NIPs pain scale use and scoring, the current state of EHR pain documentation prior to the BPA computer integration build, future state with the BPA computer integration build. The six identified pain management champions (3 on day shift and 3 on night shift) will be in-serviced by the

author on the BPA computer integration build, job aid(s), and power point presentation. Once all pain management champions have been in-serviced on the above educational intervention r/t improving procedural pain documentation (BPA computer integration build, job aid(s), and power point presentation), the educational intervention will be disseminated to all nurses via email one month prior to in-services with an attached in-service calendar.

In accordance with the PDSA model for quality improvement, the following steps are outlined:

- **Plan:** In-services to educate nurses about newborn procedural documentation in the EHR will be conducted on both day and night shift by identified unit pain management champions. The in-services will be conducted in groups and one-on-one sessions until all nurses on the unit have completed the educational intervention.
- **Do:** One month after the educational intervention, the assistant nurse manager will run the EHR BPA audit and workbench reports to see if there was a change in nursing documentation compliance of neonatal procedural pain. The audits will be run one month after the completion of all in-services and monthly thereafter to ensure compliance. All audit data will be reviewed and evaluated by the assistant nurse manager. Increased compliance in neonatal procedural pain documentation after in-services will be considered as positive since prior to this in-service the nurses had no place to document a bedside procedures.

- Study: The assistant nurse manager will analysis the data, measure outcomes, compare the data to predictions, and summarize what was learned. The outcome measures should demonstrate over time whether the change has led to sustainable improvement. The assistant nurse manager will report results at monthly unit staff meetings.
- Act: Decide whether the change was effective or ineffective as implemented or plan a new cycle of educational interventions until neonatal procedural pain documentation reaches greater than 30%. Run reports on a monthly basis and report findings on a quarterly basis and offer continuous aggregate and individual feedback to nurses about improved neonatal procedural pain documentation compliance.

Procedures

After full integration of the IT computer build into the EHR and all RNs in the maternal/newborn unit have been in-serviced on the neonatal procedural pain computer integration, BPA and workbench audit reports will be run. Aggregate feedback will be reported to nurses at monthly staff meetings to share the audit results. Any observable change in increased nursing pain documentation will demonstrate that a behavior change has occurred in relation to neonatal pain assessment and documentation as confirmed by unit pain management champion chart audits that will be disseminated at monthly unit staff meetings. Once improvements are considered adequate greater than 50%, quarterly reports will be generated and reported to staff.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Although there is evidence to support the need to treat and alleviate neonatal pain due to unfavorable adverse side effects that may alter childhood growth and development, neonatal pain continues to be untreated or unrelieved. There is evidence to support that reliable pain scales are effective at measuring and identifying neonatal pain yet not all nurses used them. Barriers that prevent the adequate management of neonatal pain include nurse's lack of knowledge and their attitudes surrounding neonatal pain. Knowledge lacks include how to assess neonatal pain and lack of competence to adequately administer pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions.

Changing nurses' behaviors by translating best evidence in clinical practice can be attempted using methods such as Audit and Feedback (AF), use of Printed Educational Material (PEMS), in-services, and Clinical Decisions Support (CDS) Best Practice Advisories (BPAs) electronic interventions to target specific nurse behaviors. Audit and feedback involves regular feedback about discrepancies in clinical performance with established guidelines. Printed educational materials can be used in with AF to improve provider knowledge and abilities during in-services. Finally, the use of informatics or CDS, electronic interventions, although a relatively new concept, may further help change nurses behaviors surrounding documentation adherence by use of computer based reminders and on-screen prompts at the point of care. Of note, the request to add electronic documentation of pain interventions for painful procedures in neonates has spurred hospital-wide interest in improving documentation for pain and in aiding best

practice advisories for pain management and documentation to the electronic health record of patients beyond neonates in the hospital.

Recommendations

Following full implementation of this quality improvement project, the planned evaluation will be determine to ascertain if the combination of neonatal procedural pain management computer integration build, educational intervention, and audit and feedback by the assistant nurse manager were effective in improving documentation of neonatal procedural pain management. The computer integration build will be assessed for workability when it goes live for implementation. Nurses' knowledge about neonatal procedural pain management will be assessed by a post-test following the in-service education. Most importantly, audit results will be tracked to demonstrate the presence (or absence) of documentation of neonatal procedural pain management. It is anticipated that the implementation of the pain management documentation fields will not only allow appropriate documentation of nursing interventions, but also will increase the likelihood that appropriate pain management occurs due to best practice advisory flags that remind nurses to perform these important pain interventions.

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APPENDIX A
TABLES OF EVIDENCE

Table 1

Summary Table: Assessing and Managing Procedural Pain in Newborns

Author, Year, Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
Asadi-Noghabi et al., 2014 Purpose: to ascertain understanding, viewpoint, and implementation of pain management practices of nurses working in units that care for newborns in Iran.	Descriptive analytical study.	A university hospital in Iran that cares for newborn patients during the month of August in 2011, included 50 nurses and nursing assistants.	Structured questionnaire was used to investigate understanding (28 items), viewpoint (20 items) and implementation practices (5 items).	Understanding pain management: Mean = 13.51 (48.2%) out of 28 Attitudes towards pain: Mean = 54.22 out of 60. 90% of participants demonstrated positive attitudes regarding neonates' pain assessment and measurement. Performance in pain management: Mean score for how nurse's implement practices 4.22 out of 10. Increased understanding of pain was correlated with increased education $p < .05$. Use of pharmacological methods: 100% used medications sometimes Use of non-pharmacological methods: 100% states	Result demonstrated that the nurses had inadequate understanding about pain assessment and low levels of implementing pain reduction methods. Nevertheless demonstrated encouraging viewpoints for managing neonatal pain.

Author, Year, Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
<p>Cong et al., 2013</p> <p>Purpose: To examine newborn nurses' understanding and implementation practices about neonatal pain management practices.</p>	<p>A cross-sectional descriptive survey design.</p>	<p>Neonatal nurses were invited via NANN membership website or by email to complete a web-based questionnaire.</p> <p>Suitability sample: 237 newborn nurses with NANN membership received a researcher developed 36 question questionnaire with a Likert scale and open ended questions (2).</p> <p>Criteria for inclusion: newborn nurses that speak English, willing to partake online study.</p>	<p>Study was administered electronically.</p> <p>Questionnaire focused on 5 characteristics of nurses' views of newborn pain 1: understanding and views, 2: usage of validation scales, 3: usage of pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions, 4: rules/procedures, and 5: barriers and strategies on a 5-point Likert scale.</p>	<p>they used them sometimes.</p> <p>Knowledge and view about neonatal pain:</p> <p>Neonates capable of suffering pain = 88% SA.</p> <p>Minor procedures cause pain = 36% SA.</p> <p>Long term adversarial effects = 45% strongly agreed.</p> <p>Nurses' awareness of pain assessment in NICU:</p> <p>Unit utilizes neonatal pain assessment tool regularly basis = 54% SA.</p> <p>Confident in use of the neonatal pain assessment tool on my unit" = 38% SA.</p> <p>Confidence in identifying physiological and behavior pain indicators = 43% strongly agree.</p> <p>Confidence in interpreting pain totals = 27% SA.</p>	<p>Nurses' views regarding the adequate management of newborn pain was associated with preparation, use of accurate pain scales, and evidenced based practices.</p> <p>Obstacles involved lack of understanding, observed fears regarding the adverse effects of pain medication and inappropriate understanding of pain indications, time constraints, and absence of confidence in pain valuation</p>

Author, Year, Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
				<p>Nurses' views of pain interventions in the NICU:</p> <p>Neonatal pain well managed" = 7% SA. Confidence using non-pharmacological pain relieving methods = 33% SA.</p> <p>Strategies/Procedures that include family participation in pain management:</p> <p>Cognizant of pain managing strategies/practices = 37% SA. Pain management guidelines/protocols clear comprehensive" = 19% SA. Changing pain managing practices = 13% SA.</p>	<p>scales.</p> <p>Gaps were observed in awareness, verification, and practices in newborn valuation and pain management practices.</p>
<p>Akuma & Jordan, 2012</p> <p>Purpose: To describe nurses' and doctors' knowledge regarding neonatal pain assessment and management in</p>	<p>Descriptive cross sectional survey.</p>	<p>The study took place from January to August, 2011 in the United Kingdom and included nurses and doctors that worked NICUs (7).</p>	<p>The questionnaire encompassed 7 methods and 4 gestational age classifications.</p> <p>Respondents' were awareness and views of</p>	<p>62 doctors and 137 nurses responded. Findings were based on 199 questionnaires (18 incomplete).</p> <p>Knowledge:</p>	<p>A need for guidelines, policies, pain assessment scales, and formal training to manage</p>

Author, Year, Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
Neonatal Intensive Care Units.			<p>newborn pain assessment and management, clinical practice was assessed.</p> <p>8 Open ended questions (8) and multiple choice (24) were structured by use of Likert measures.</p> <p>0 = no pain, 10 = worse pain, or true/false; <, =, >, not ever/hardly/frequently/ generally/constantly.</p>	<p>Nurses rated pain significantly greater than doctors for all procedures, with the exception of heel stick (p < .05).</p> <p>Nurses rated intensity of neonatal pain to be higher than adults at 31.4% doctors 25.8%.</p> <p>Practice:</p> <p>Analgesia & comfort methods</p> <p>Never use analgesia for heel stick:</p> <p>45.5% of doctors, 29.8% of nurses.</p> <p>Usage of comfort methods for procedures: 3.3% doctors and 6.2% nurses never used comfort measures.</p> <p>Response to questions re: clinical practice guideline and training:</p>	neonatal pain effectively.

Author, Year, Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Have you received training on neonatal pain and analgesia in your current post?” • Yes: doctors = 20.97% and nurses = 31.23%. • “Did your unit have a neonatal pain management guideline?” • Yes: doctors = 46.77% and nurses = 62.04%. 	
<p>Walter-Nicolet et al., 2010</p> <p>Purpose: To assess the frequency of analgesia use for invasive procedures.</p>	<p>Literature Review.</p>	<p>2 studies in 2 different countries investigated frequency of analgesic use for invasive procedures in the first 14 days of admission to the NICU.</p> <p>Study 1:</p> <p>Documented the use of analgesia for painful events during the first 14 days in NICU in 151 neonates.</p> <p>Study 2:</p>	<p>Pain was assessed by one-dimensional or multidimensional pain scales.</p> <p>Multidimensional scales include behavioral and physiological indicators.</p>	<p>The average neonate experienced 14 procedures/day.</p> <p>26/31 of the procedures listed were appraised to be painful.</p> <p>Less than 13% of neonates were given preventative analgesia.</p> <p>Pain assessment tools identified by potential painful circumstance and need for intervention.</p>	<p>Despite progress in the management of neonatal pain, pain still exists.</p> <p>Effective pain management is challenging in neonates.</p>

Author, Year, Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
Morrow et al., 2010	RCT.	Documented management of painful procedures during the first 14 days in NICU for 430 neonates. 42 newborns were enrolled in the study. n = 22 newborns in investigational group, n = 22, and n = 20 newborns in control group were not held wrapped/embraced.	Instrument: Pain was measured by NIPS at 2 points in time (before HS and after).	Most identified painful procedures: nasal aspiration, heel sticks, and tracheal suctioning. Mean NIPS scores in investigational group was considerably less mean = 1.3 and SD = .9. Control group mean = 2.7 and SD = 1.3 t (40) = -4.48; p < .001.	Neonates that were wrapped and embraced demonstrated higher levels of pain relief during the heel lance procedure in comparison to those that were not.
Pölkki et al., 2010	A cross-sectional, descriptive and correlational survey design.	362 Finish nurses (RNs and PNs) from 5 university hospitals. The questionnaire mailed to ward sisters in April 2006 to be forwarded to nurses participating in survey. None of questionnaires excluded due to data omission.	362 respondents working in NICU/monitoring units were asked to complete survey and return in sealed envelope to ward sisters. Data collection lasted 3 weeks. Response rare was < 50% in 3 units. Questionnaires were resent May-June, 2006. 257 questionnaires were returned, average response rate 71%.	Nurses that had between 3-5 years of nursing education comprised 89% of respondents: 11%, PNs with 2-3 years of education. Nurses' attitudes towards pain assessment and importance of using pain instruments = 40% totally agreed. Assessing pain in newborns is equated to good pain valuation and documentation practices	Overall respondents demonstrated positive attitudes toward conducting pain assessments in the NICU. However only 40% believed in using pain scales. Gaps in nurses'

Author, Year, Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
				<p>= 62 agreed totally.</p> <p>Demographics factors associated with nurses' outlooks and opinions about pain valuation were statistically correlated.</p> <p>p = 0.001 with nurse's attitudes and documentation practices.</p>	<p>knowledge still exist and there is a need for EB guidelines for pain assessment and ongoing pain assessment education.</p>
<p>Gradin & Eriksson, 2010</p> <p>Purpose: To examine if pain assessment was implemented in Sweden NICUs and by which method.</p>	<p>15 year Longitudinal survey study.</p>	<p>A 7 question multiple choice questionnaire with space for free text was distributed in January, 2008 to 37 NICU units in Sweden. 95 % Response rate.</p> <p>Unit identification was not used in study.</p>	<p>The questionnaire was present to the charge nurses of NICUs in Sweden.</p> <p>The questionnaire was generally the same as preceding studies with the adding of pain totals and pain valuation approaches were put into place after the previous surveys were completed.</p>	<p>83% units stated they attempted to assess pain.</p> <p>44% utilized a structured system for pain assessment.</p> <p>94% stated there was a need for structured pain assessment.</p> <p>40% performed routine pain assessments.</p> <p>66% stated they provided material about pain assessment to new staff.</p>	<p>Increase in units attempting to assess pain in 2008 = 83% from 1993 = 64% (original study) increase in use of structured pain scales in 2008 = 48% from 1993 = 10%.</p> <p>Although nurse demonstrated an understanding about pain valuation and its importance, it was not</p>

Author, Year, Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
<p>Taddio et al., 2009</p> <p>Purpose: To ascertain the effects of numerous vs. few painful procedure using a sugar solution vs. placebo on hyperalgesia.</p>	<p>RCT.</p>	<p>Subjects were randomized into two groups:</p> <p>n = 120 healthy neonates, n = 120 healthy neonates born to mothers with gestational diabetes.</p> <p>Randomization into a sugar solution group and placebo group was done preceding heel sticks in the first 48 hours of life as well as 2 exposure groups corresponding to the number of procedures > 5 or < 4.</p>	<p>PIPP totals did not vary during diaper change.</p> <p>Veni-puncture was noted to be but expressive of a nociception and hyperalgesia.</p> <p>Crying, PIPP, and VAS totals were decreased during veni-puncture when a sugar solutions was used $p > 0.05$.</p>	<p>The use of a sugar solution for the alleviation of pain due to frequent painful procedures in the initial 24 hours after birth did not does not stop increase of hyperalgesia.</p> <p>An increase in the number of newborns from mothers with diabetes was noted in the exposure group with high heel sticks but this did was not confounding factor.</p>	<p>reflected in their documentation practices.</p> <p>In comparison to the group with minimal exposure to needle sticks, newborns in the increased exposure group had an augmented pain reaction throughout succeeding needle sticks away from the location of the preceding needle stick as evaluated by the use of PIPP pain scale.</p>
<p>Weissman et al., 2009</p> <p>Purposes: To 1) Evaluate various approaches for pain management in neonates.</p> <p>2) Assess the concordance among behavior and cardiac response to pain in full-term</p>	<p>Prospective Study.</p>	<p>Healthy neonates born at > 37 weeks gestation and Apgar totals of greater than within 5 minutes of life.</p> <p>180 term newborns experiencing heel lancing for routine NBS assigned to 6 sets:</p>	<p>NFCS was used to measure crying, cardiac response at three different intervals in the heel stick process.</p>	<p>Breastfeeding or formula feeding newborns were demonstrated the lowest rise in heart rate 21 and 23 beats/minute. $p < .01$.</p> <p>The lowermost NFCS was 2.3 and 2.9 ($p < .001$).</p>	<p>Neonates with no pain management displayed highest pain expression in comparison with newborns with pain</p>

Author, Year, Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
newborns when a needle stick was performed.		1) Control group: no pain medication. 2) NNS. 3) Mother's embrace. 4) Use of sugar solution. 5) Infant formula use. 6) Breastfeeding.		The lowermost cry length was 5-13 seconds, vs. 49; $p < .001$. The lowermost reduction in parasympathetic tone was -2 and -2.4, vs. 1.2; $p < .02$ in comparison to other groups.	control. Any measure of pain relief is optimal to no measure of pain relief while heel lancing procedures.
Lavanya et al., 2009 Purpose: To evaluate the awareness, viewpoint, and implementation practices between health care providers concerning pain in children.	Prospective descriptive study.	An inclusion criterion was open to Nurses and Physicians in a pediatric ward of a tertiary care hospital in north India. The study included 77 respondents.	A 24 question semi structured questionnaire was developed. 18 questions graded on a 5 point Likert tool and 6 open ended questions. Areas evaluated included understanding of pain tools, pain valuation, and pain relief methods measures.	Response rates: 94% of nurses and 83% of doctors. 61% of nurses completed questionnaire. 66% of nurses completed their General Nursing Midwifery (GNM). 34% of nurses had completed their BS nursing. The questionnaire was completed by 39% of pediatric residents (47%	Health care providers are able to classify pain and indicate that verbal pain validation is the most significant predictor of pain intensity. Findings stress the requisite to increase awareness of pain validation and pain evaluation in

Author, Year, Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
				<p>were senior and 53% were junior residents).</p> <p>Awareness about pain scales:</p> <p>Pain validation tools meant for adult patients = 9% agreed.</p> <p>Used pain tool with children = 45%.</p> <p>Pain was indicative of crying in all child age groups.</p> <p>Inadequate pain management consequences:</p> <p>1/3 did not report any.</p> <p>Others listed psychological problems (25%).</p> <p>Performing procedures safely (10%).</p> <p>Knowledge, attitude and practices related to pain control measures.</p>	children.

Author, Year, Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
				<p>62% felt that non-pharmacological methods control pain more effectively than drugs.</p> <p>Most common method was distraction.</p> <p>77% of healthcare providers showed willingness for parent presence during minor invasive procedures.</p> <p>94% agreed they should explain in simple words the procedure</p>	

Note. BS= Bachelor Degree in Science; EB = Evidenced Based; GM = General Nursing Midwifery; HS = Heel Stick; M = Mean; NANN = National Association of Neonatal Nurses; NFCS = Neonatal Facial Coding System; NICU = Neonatal Intensive Care Unit; NIPS = Neonatal Infant Pain Scale; NBS = Newborn Screen; PIPP = Pediatric Infant Pain Scale; RCT = Randomized Control Trial; RNs = Registered Nurses; SA = Strongly Agreed; SD = Standard Deviation; VAS = Visual Analog Scale

Table 2

Summary Table: Barriers to Managing Procedural Pain

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
<p>Twycross & Collins, 2013</p> <p>Purpose: To determine nurses' understandings, obstacles, and mediators to effectual pain control.</p> <p>To discover nurses' views of :</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) How effectively measure and manage pain. 2) Obstacles to effective pain management. 3) Usefulness of hospital protocols. 	Focus groups.	<p>30 nurses participated in a mandatory study in a hospital in South England between May and September, 2010.</p> <p>The study consisted of 2 modified focus groups held during the lunch hour.</p> <p>On 2 days Guidelines and protocols were implemented and included pain validation scale, and medicines.</p>	<p>Participants were assigned into groups of 4-6, handed a flipchart and important questions regarding:</p> <p>Pain assessment, pain management, child-parent engagement, facilitators and obstacles.</p> <p>Participants were expected to document their opinions about each question in a flip chart.</p>	<p>Data from flip charts was arranged into a word document.</p> <p>Pain validation and pain controlling routines (with a subcategory correlated to discharge information handed to parents).</p> <p>Family participation in pain control, hurdles to validation and controlling pain efficiently.</p> <p>Participants identified obstacles related to staff, children, parent, and organization.</p> <p>Results identified:</p> <p>Nurses opinions that pain management is tantamount with analgesia administration. Some nurses may not view pain management as a priority.</p> <p>Lack of knowledge among nurses was regarded as a hurdle to optimal pain management.</p>	<p>Gaps exist between nurses and physicians knowledge regarding the management of infant pain.</p> <p>Strategies are needed to verify that hospital personnel are aware of hospital protocols, their use in clinical practice, and the influence of organizational culture on pain management practices.</p>
Cong et al., 2013	Cross sectional survey study.	343 American neonatal nurses.	Survey questionnaire instrument focused on	Knowledge and beliefs neonates experience pain:	Nurse's responses regarding neonatal pain

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations	
Purpose: To examine newborn nurses views, understanding, and clinical practice of pain management in the US and China.		106 Chinese neonatal nurses.	five facets of newborn pain:	A: 96% & C: 97% agreed.	reflected adequate knowledge in general pain concepts.	
		Inclusion criteria:	1: Knowledge and views.	Newborn pain has long term consequences:	Knowledge deficits related to several topics were found such as babies that were not born at term demonstrated increased pain and developed long term after-effects of pain.	
		Nurses working with neonates, English or Chinese speaking.	2: Use of validation scales.	A: 10% & C: 21% agreed.	Pain assessment tool is used on their unit:	
		American nurses were recruited by email through NANN webpage/direct email to complete online survey.	3: Use of pharmacological and non-pharmacological methods.	A: 65% & C: 43% agreed.	Tool was accurate to measure neonatal pain:	Most reported regular use of pain assessment tools; fewer agreed that the tool used was appropriate.
		Chinese nurses were recruited from 3 teaching hospital NICUs/nurseries in Beijing, China.	4: Hospital policies and family involvement.	A: 60% & C: 40% agreed.	Pain intervention	The survey findings revealed worries that pain has not been adequately managed in numerous NICUs in the US and China.
		Demographic characteristics.	5: Obstacles and interventions.		Felt pharmacologic/Non-pharmacologic needed for invasive procedures:	
			5 point Likert tool was used in 36 questions surrounding # 1-4.	A: 87% & C: 31%.	Felt confident in their use of pain medication for treating neonatal pain:	Additional research is necessary to resolve questions of insufficient preparation and instruction, deficiency of validated pain tools, and the absence of evidence based protocols.
			2 open ended questions used to discover possible barriers to pain management and strategies.		A: 83% & C: 58%.	
					Acknowledged effectiveness of non-pharmacological methods:	

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
				A: 61% & C: 78%.	
				Neonatal pain well managed:	
				A: 44% & C: 56%.	
				Pain guidelines/protocols and family participation	
				Aware of pain management guideline/protocols:	
				A: 79% & C: 44%.	
				Felt protocols were clear:	
				A: 53% & C: 27%.	
				Barriers and strategies:	
				Felt advocacy was important to improve neonatal pain care:	
				A: 91% & C: 85%.	
				Resistance to change due to lack of communication among doctors and nurses:	
				A: 44% & C: 30%.	
				Lack of knowledge:	
				A: 23% & C: 24%.	
				Time constraints:	

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
				A: 14 & C: 39%. Lacked trust in assessment tools: A: 13% & C: 6%	
Czarnecki et al., 2011 Purpose: To ascertain by what methods nurses defined optimum pain control and how they observed potential obstacles inhibiting their aptitude to provide optimum pain control.	Cross sectional design survey.	A cross sectional design evaluating apparent obstacles to optimum pain control was conducted in a 236 bed pediatric hospital in Wisconsin. Inclusion for study was voluntary, anonymous, and informed consent implied if they participated in the study.	Surveys were disseminated to RNs by the manager, APN, or designee assigned to each unit. RN's returned survey to management, designees, and pain center at 3-4 weeks. 970 surveys were disseminated to all RNs. Exclusion criteria: Nurse's aides, interns, and students. All data was kept under lock and key and password protected. 35 question "Barriers to Optimal Pain Management" 18 possible obstacles classified on an 11-point Likert tool.	The five most significant barriers to pain management were: 1: Not adequate/insufficient MD orders. 2: Insufficient pre-medication prior to procedures. 3: Not enough time to pre-medicate before procedures. 4: Low priority given to pain management by doctors. 5: Parents not wishing their child to receive pain meds Nurses rated these areas as low barriers to optimal pain management. Limitations in personal knowledge of pain management. Limitations in own ability to assess pain management.	Results of this study support earlier study finding which identified a lack of MD orders and lack of MD support in the treatment of optimal pain management as barriers. In order to improve pain management you need support from the organization, MDs, RNs, and families.

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
			Procedural pain management queries and documentation methods were tallied. Impact of APS from 0-10 indicating poor to optimum.	Low importance given to pain management by nurse.	
Byrd, Gonzales, & Parsons, 2009 Purpose: To explore obstacles faced by neonatal intensive care nurses when attempting to control pain in newborns.	Descriptive survey study.	Probability sampling from a list of nurse's in California that had up-to-date membership in NANN of which 90 voluntarily participated.	A 37 question survey questionnaire was mailed to 300 NANN members; 90/102 questionnaires were used.	Obstacles associated with pain control practices and personal views. Pain adequately controlled on the unit they work = 45% agreed. Pain control is an important quality metric to their co-workers = 80% agreed. 61% agreed pain management is important to physicians. Obstacles associated with related to nursing education and pain validation scales = 94% confidence with their pain assessment skills. 44% obtained sufficient preparation during the orientation process. 55% unit provides ongoing educations about newborn pain	Gaps still exist between knowledge of pain management and putting that knowledge into practice. Increasing provider knowledge is essential to adequately control neonatal pain and to address strategies to overcome barriers.

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
				<p>management.</p> <p>87% regularly use pain assessment tools when assessing newborn pain.</p> <p>79% felt confident in using them.</p> <p>63% pain validation scales used on their unit were suitable and correctly measured newborn pain.</p> <p>Obstacles associated to organizational protocols:</p> <p>91% of nurses' aware unit pain guidelines/protocols.</p> <p>63% believed unit guidelines were easy to follow and evidenced based.</p> <p>10% time constraints and acuity affected their capacity to manage newborn pain.</p> <p>59% of physicians & 68% of nurses were open to new evidenced based guidelines. Obstacles associated with effective and safe pain control practices.</p>	

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample/ Setting	Procedures and Methods	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
				79% of nurses agreed that non-pharmacological methods are effective.	
				68% felt apprehension in administering opioids to neonates due to respiratory depression.	
				93% felt the use of opioids would cause addiction.	

Note. A = American; APN = Advanced Practice Nurse; C = Chinese; CHW = Children’s Hospital of Wisconsin; MD = Medical Doctor; MDs = Medical Doctors; NANN = National Association of Neonatal Nurses; NICU = Neonatal Intensive Care Unit; RNs = Registered Nurses; US = United States.

Table 3

Summary Table: Systematic Reviews: Changing Nurse Behaviors

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample	Review Procedures	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
Ivers et al., 2014 Purpose: To broaden results of Cochrane review of AF; to discover the progress of evidence supporting QI intervention.	Systematic Review.	140 RCTs, 98 comparisons from 62 studies (met inclusion). Studies took place in US and Canada and outpatient was the most common setting.	Secondary analysis from previous Cochrane systematic review of AF.	140 RCTs, 98 comparisons from 62 studies. 85% of studies feedback delivered by investigator or other. 47% of studies FB only given once. 61% of studies FB did not have goal or action plan. Median effect or IQR had little change from 2002 IQR = 1.65-10.85 to present IQR = 1.04-10.90.	AF is most effective when given by supervisor, respected colleague, given in a frequent manner, used to decrease targeted behaviors, baseline performance is low, and not given to physicians.
Squires et al., 2014 Purpose: To evaluate the efficacy of multifaceted interventions compared to single interventions in changing healthcare providers' behavior in the clinical setting.	Overview of systematic reviews.	Used Rx for Change database. Inclusion criteria: Reviews that compared effectiveness of multifaceted interventions to single intervention to change the behaviors of healthcare	Screening included assessing full text article for moderate and high quality reviews that were aimed at healthcare professionals in Rx for Change database published on or before May 1, 2013. Data extraction criteria: Publication date, location, populace,	Of 233 reviews only 25 met inclusion criteria. 9 studies reported 2 analytical approaches, 2 reviews reported effect size/dose response statistical analysis and indirect comparisons. Effectiveness of multifaceted interventions effect size/ dose response statistical analysis (=3). Direct comparison (= 8) reported	Not sufficient evidence to support those MF interventions are more efficacious than S interventions.

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample	Review Procedures	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
		providers, whose methodological quality was rated moderate/high, and referenced the Rx for Change database. No reviews were excluded based on type of health care professional, outcome, study design, or date of publication.	number of primary studies, intervention, comparisons, conclusions, and all findings associated to the efficacy of multifaceted compared to single interventions. 3 analytic approaches reported robustness: 1. Effect size/dose response statistical analyses. 2. Direct comparisons of efficiency of multifaceted compared to single interventions. 3. Indirect comparisons of the efficiency of multifaceted compared to single intervention by comparing multifaceted to controls vs. single to controls.	a direct comparison of MF to S. Indirect comparisons (= 23) reported indirect comparisons of MF to Single by comparing MF to controls and S to controls. 9 of these reviews reported a statistically significant dose response (2) or a non-significant response (7). 15 of these reviews reported indirect comparisons of MF to S interventions demonstrated similar efficacy for MF and S when they were compared to the controls. Remaining 8 reviews 6 demonstrated S effective whilst MS demonstrated varied effectiveness.	
Forsetlund et al., 2012 Purpose: To evaluate effects of educational gathering on	Systematic Review.	81 RCTs evaluated effects of educational gatherings on measures of professional practice on patient	2 independent authors mined information and evaluated the quality of the study. Low or moderate bias risk studies provided	Based on 30 trials median corrected RD in accordance with anticipated practice was 6% when any interventional method was used that contained an educational gathering were the educational element was	Educational gatherings alone or a combination with other interventions may increase healthcare provider practices and increase patient effects. The effect, although small

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample	Review Procedures	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
provider practice outcomes.		outcomes. 49 studies were included in the study. 81 trials included 11,000 healthcare professionals. 14 studies excluded from original review because they did not meet criteria for inclusion.	baseline information incorporated in the primary analysis and weighted based on the number of healthcare providers taking part in the study. RD for dichotomous conclusions attuned for baseline adherence and constant outcomes. Control group median subsequent to intervention was adjusted for starting point performance. Features (10) were measured to elucidate heterogeneity of the effect estimates utilizing weighed meta- regression.	associated with no intervention. Educational gatherings alone had comparable effects based on 21 appraisals in 19 trials overall.	and similar to other types of CE and AF Strategies, noted to increase attendance by using diversified shared and educational presentations that focus on outcomes. Educational meetings alone not noted to change complex behaviors. 36 associations were made with median adjusted RD in accordance with preferred practice = 6%, interquartile range = 1.8-15.9 when any intervention in which educational gatherings was a component was compared to no intervention.
Ivers et al., 2012 Purpose: To evaluate the effects of audit and feedback on healthcare provider practices on patient outcome measures and to distinguish	Randomized trials.	140 studies reported audit and feedback. Accurately measured health care professionals practice on patient outcomes.	Primary outcomes & median absolute RD was calculated in accordance with anticipated practice conformity with dichotomous outcome measures and median percentage variations to control group for	After excluding high bias studies 82 associations from 49 studies. Assessed any intervention in that audit and feedback was a principal component of standard care and measured its effects on professional practice. There was an absolute increase	For the most part audit and feedback serve as important interventions to improve professional practice even if done in small increments. The success of audit and feedback is dependent on reference point performance and the manner in which

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample	Review Procedures	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
between features that elucidate differences in the usefulness of audit and feedback.		From 108, 70 studies met criteria. When there was an increased possibility of bias studies were excluded. 82 associations from 49 studies featured dichotomous outcome measures.	uninterrupted outcome measures. Median effect size was weighted by the total of healthcare professionals partaking in each study. Elements related the effectiveness of methods were reviewed such as the configuration of the feedback, source, rate of recurrence, guidelines for improvement, course of change needed, reference point performance, profession of receiver, and risk of bias within the trial.	(0.5% to 16% and weighted RD was 4%) in healthcare provider compliance with anticipated practice. For patient outcomes 8 comparisons from 5 studies demonstrated continuous outcome measures. Multi-variable, meta-regression showed feedback might be more beneficial when reference point performance is decreased, when the information is given by a supervisor, data is presented more than once, it is delivered in verbal and written forms, and comprises clear objectives and an action plan.	feedback is delivered.
Farmer et al., 2012 Purpose: To ascertain the usefulness of printed educational materials in refining process conclusions involving the behavior of health providers and patient care outcomes.	RCT's, CCTS, CBAs, and ITS studies.	RCTs, CCTs, measured CBAs and ITS which measured the effect of PEMs on health providers practice and patient care outcomes. No limits on objective methods of professional performance such as the volume of	4 reviewers carry out data extraction individually utilizing an adapted account of EPOC information collecting checklist. Differences were solved by reviewers and mediators. Statistical analysis established on dichotomous, continuous process	23 studies were included RCT's associating printed educational materials to no intervention demonstrated complete RD: + 4% on category process outcomes such as request for x-ray, prescribing medications, and smoking cessation. A relative RD on constant process outcomes (arbitration change, x-rays, request for practice).	PEMs appeared to have small useful effects on professional practice when compared to no intervention. Printed educational materials alone may have a positive effect on process outcomes not on patient outcomes. Although there are a wide range of effects defined for PEMs, clinical importance of detected effect size is not known.

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample	Review Procedures	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
To discover if the effect of characteristics of PEMs will effect procedure outcomes comprising the behavior of health professionals and patient care outcomes.		tests ordered or the amount of prescriptions, or patient healthcare outcomes.	outcomes, patient outcomes. Results were compared using standard measure of presentation whenever possible. Separate reports completed for each study with a median effect size for each kind of outcome all across studies.	Similar findings for ITS studies with meaningful larger effect sizes detected relative RD from 0.07% to 31%. Median effect size was negative 4% for patient outcome category measures (screenings, returning to work, and smoking cessation). 2 studies illustrated declines in continuous patient outcome data (depression score and smoking cession attempts) of -10.0% and -20.5%. 2 studies associating PEMs and instruction outreach demonstrated no statistically significant changes among the groups.	Data was lacking to derive optimization of educational materials, and usefulness of educational instruments related to other interventions is not clear.
Costa et al., 2009 Purpose: To evaluate the effects of audit and feedback on the practice of professionals in OB.	Systematic review.	Before and after intervention study in an OB unit in Brazil.	6 EB audit criteria were chosen for monitoring and were prospectively gathered from all admissions to L&D for 3 months Intervention: Seminars and workshops were administered with baseline results and 11 AF studies (used to identify the 6 EB criteria) discussion of	Pre-intervention 664 deliveries. Episiotomy: Selective 57%. Selective in nulliparous 48%. Antibiotics prophylaxis in CS 97%. Prophylactic uterotonic-3 rd stage of labor 99%.	Clinical audit and feedback of OB care resulted in improved outcomes in 2 out of 6 criteria studied and may play an important role in improving quality of care.

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample	Review Procedures	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
			RHL.	Continuous EFM 46%.	
			Followed by audits 3 months.	Companion during childbirth 59%.	
				Induction 41 weeks 67%.	
				Post-intervention: 628 deliveries.	
				Episiotomy: Selective 48%.	
				Selective in nulliparous 37%.	
				Antibiotics prophylaxis in CS 100%.	
				Prophylactic uterotonic-3 rd stage of labor 99%.	
				Continuous EFM 52%.	
				Companion during childbirth 59%.	
				Induction at 41 weeks 69%	

Note. AF = Audit and Feedback; CBAs = Controlled Before and After Studies; CCTs = Controlled Clinical Trials; CE = Continuing Education; CS = Cesarean Section; EB = Evidenced Based; EFM = External Fetal Monitoring; EPOC = Effective Practice and Organization of Care; FB = Feedback; IQR = Interquartile Range; ITS = Interrupted Time Series Analyses; L&D = Labor and Delivery; MF = Multifaceted; OB = Obstetrics; PEMs = Printed Educational Materials; RCTs = Randomized Controlled Trials; RD = Risk Difference; RHL = Reproductive Health Library; Rx = Prescription; S = Single; US = United States.

Table 4

Summary Table: Utilization and Integration of Informatics to Change Documentation Behaviors

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measure and Operational Definitions	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
Farzandipour et al., 2013 Purpose: To observe if an educational intervention can enhance the documentation of health information by residents at the Kashan University of Medical Sciences in Iran.	Pilot study with open observational design.	Academic hospital in Esfahan, Iran in 2010; 19 first year internal medicine, surgical and obstetrics resident physicians enrolled at Kashan University.	Chart Review: Baseline audit revealed documentation inadequacies and lack of knowledge in making correct diagnosis. Educational Intervention 5 hour lecture on documentation and medical coding practices. Documenting emphasis was on prevention. Coding: ICD-10 coding training and case studies Learning Objectives: Limited to labeling main diagnosis and secondary conditions, staging of neoplasms, and OB complications. Exam: After the educational	The results demonstrated that there was no progress in the quality and accurateness in documentation of obstetric diagnoses after training. No effect on documentation in the health record of diagnosis or underlying causes and clinical symptoms of disease residents p = 0.285 and p = 0.584.	Single educational sessions do not appear to be effective and multiple strategies need to be performed in order to make effective changes in ones behaviors. Buy in from staff and also buy in from leadership is necessary to conduct educational sessions that provide multiple strategies in order to demonstrate changes over time.

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measure and Operational Definitions	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
			<p>session an exam was given using copies of medical records containing pertinent health information and they were asked to code the diagnosis.</p> <p>Prospective Analysis:</p> <p>Lastly, the impact of training session on physician behavior was assessed.</p> <p>Chart review done at baseline was done again in one month after educational session and data analyzed.</p>		
<p>Issa et al., 2013</p> <p>Propose: To examine if updating a medical address grounded on EB practices of multimodal strategy would improve long-term memory retention.</p>	A pre-test/post-test control design.	<p>Condition group 37, medical students from a Midwestern medical school.</p> <p>Modified condition group 43 similar medical students.</p>	<p>Condition group received a lecture as part of core curriculum.</p> <p>Modified condition group. Received identical content with redesigned slides using Mayer's EB principles of multimedia design.</p>	<p>The adjusted condition group outscored the customary condition group on deferred tests of transference administered at 1 week (d = 0.83) and 4 weeks (d = 1.17) after lecture.</p> <p>Deferred tests of remembering given 1 week (d = 1.83) and 4 weeks (d = 0.79) after teaching.</p> <p>Modified condition group significantly surpassed traditional condition group on instantaneous tests of retention</p>	This study offers evidence supporting the application of multimedia design principles to increase a learners understanding of long-term transfer and retention.

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measure and Operational Definitions	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
Cheung et al., 2012 Purpose: To perform a synopsis of current systematic reviews to assess the usefulness of prompts in modifying professional behaviors in the clinical setting.	Overview of Systematic Reviews.	2 screeners reviewed article in Rx for Change database to find pertinent articles circulated before 9/2009. They used AMSTAR quality validation scale to measure the quality of systematic reviews. 313 reviews in RX for Change database surveyed professional provider behavior modification interventions 41 reviews of reminder interventions. Population of interest: Healthcare providers in clinical setting	The intervention needed to associate the efficacy of prompts to other interventions or control. Effectiveness was characterized as usually effective, mixed effects, and usually ineffective. Reviews were categorized into four groups for analysis grounded on their results: 1) Broad reviews all types of reminders. 2) Reviews of specific settings. 3) Reviews of precise behaviors. 4) Review of specific patient populations.	d = 1.49 and transfer if information d = 0.76. Outcomes of RCTs and studies investigating multidimensional interventions VS prompt interventions alone are offered. Of the 10 review that assessed reminders, ½ showed that prompts were in general effectual and ½ demonstrated mixed outcomes. 1 high quality showed reminders were effective. The study had 32 comparisons of on screen computer prompts on process adherence, and described a quantitative summary. The median effect size was an absolute risk difference of 4%; IQR: 1%-7% in process of care measures. The review assessed the impact of other effect changers on the efficiency of computerized reminders and established that computerized prompts that necessitated clinicians to input a reply were more likely to show a positive effect size.	Systems that are able to deliver reminders/prompts were noted to be successful in modifying health provider behaviors and improve process of care. Reminder systems that proactively reminded HCP and called for a reply were more likely to be effective in modifying HCP behavior. The effects of reminders/prompts demonstrate a + impact on clinical practice, inexpensive, and easy to give/implement in multiple settings.

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measure and Operational Definitions	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
		<p>Inclusion criteria:</p> <p>Reviews that described outcomes for professional performance 35 review published 1993-2009 were eligible for inclusion</p> <p>Exclusion:</p> <p>Reviews that observed understanding of professional behavior as an outcome.</p> <p>6 were excluded because they had been updated by a subsequent review.</p>		<p>5 reviews assessed reminders in a particular healthcare settings 4of 5 reviews demonstrated + results in outpatient/ambulatory care settings.</p> <p>The review were low quality on AMSTAR less than 5</p> <p>14 reviews observed at prompts for particular behaviors such as prescribing changes.</p> <p>All studies showed positive results.</p> <p>4 reviews had AMSTAR totals greater than 5 and showed prompts had a + effect on professional behavior.</p> <p>Another study assessed the effect of reminders on nursing practices; the majority of the studies that were suitable for this review demonstrated that the intervention was effective.</p>	
George et al., 2010	Descriptive study.	18 question survey administered online over a 4 month period Students informed about study through posters	Undergraduate and graduate nursing students received PDA before clinical rotation and the study looked at PDA use by undergraduate and graduate nursing	<p>Results indicated that 9% used their PDA weekly, 50% used them daily.</p> <p>96% of students stated they used their PDA in clinical are, 67% in the classroom, and 56% for personal use.</p>	<p>Utilization of PDAs in the clinical setting may be useful to improve a nurse's efficiency and improve patient outcomes.</p> <p>Staff training is imperative for successful</p>

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measure and Operational Definitions	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
		and email. 89 undergraduate, 42 graduate. 1 did not indicate educational level. Students fit criteria of being in a nursing program and were sent survey, 54% response rate.	students.	During a usual day 98% of students used them 1-3 times and 21% stated they used them 7-10 times per day. 71% of students stated the use of PDA increased their efficiency and 100% stated they noted. PDAs as an efficient educational strategy. Barriers: 48% of students verbalized they experienced obstacles to PDA use and 23% cited insufficient training, and 15 cited a lack of understanding or uneasiness with technology.	implementation of the device and to reduce barriers to use.
Shojania et al., 2009 Purpose: To assess the effects of prompts sent to healthcare providers at the point of care on processes and outcomes of care.	Systematic Reviews.	Studies included RCTs, quasi- randomized trials Participants included any study in which included greater than 50% physicians. Exclusions were studies targeted dentists, nurses, pharmacists or other.	Operational perspective was to evaluate point of care computer reminders for physicians at the point they were engaged in prescribing meds, documenting in medical record. The prompt was sent via computer system normally utilized by physicians targeted by intervention by EHR or computer order entry.	2036 citations of which 1662 were excluded initially and later 374. 29 articles met inclusion criteria. 6 quasi-RCTs described greater improvements in process adherence than 26 randomized comparisons: 7%, IQR: 1% to 28% vs. 3%, IQR 1% to 16% but was not statistically significant due to sample size did not compare with effect size.	While several studies have revealed significant advances at the point of care with computer reminders it is worrisome that the bulk of studies have demonstrated minor improvements amid a range of process types. Future research is needed to identify central factors associated with the target quality indicator or the design of the prompt that will consistently predict

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measure and Operational Definitions	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
			<p>The prompt was sent to the computer used the most by the clinician using a pop-up on the screen that required the user to perform a feature.</p> <p>The prompt is specified for the user of the computer accountable for the applicable clinical activity.</p>	<p>US studies reported slightly larger improvements in process adherence: 5%, IQR 2% to 23% vs. 1%, IQR 0.4% to 6% for non-US studies were not statistically significant.</p> <p>In institutions that had an clinical informatics for a long period of time had higher rates of process adherence.</p> <p>4 Studies from Brigham and Women's Hospital demonstrated higher performance adherence 16.8%, IQR: 9% to 26% vs. 3%, IQR: 1% to 12%; p = 0.04</p> <p>32 comparisons defined process adherence outcomes consisted of 18 that assessed a computer prompt vs. normal care.</p> <p>14 appraised a computer-based reminder and another quality improvement intervention VS this same co-intervention in the control group.</p> <p>Comparisons concerning no co-intervention, computer reminder alone vs. normal care showed a median improvement in process adherence of 6%, IQR: 2% to 24%.</p>	<p>greater improvements in care.</p> <p>Although it appears that this intervention alone may not be significant enough to change documentation behaviors; hospitals that have long term used the clinical information system demonstrated marked improvement with this intervention.</p>

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Key Designs/Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measure and Operational Definitions	Results/Findings	Author Conclusions/ Limitations
				While studies of multidimensional interventions, computer reminders plus additional interventions vs. those with additional interventions alone demonstrated a median improvement in process adherence of only 2%, IQR: 0.0% to 6%; p = 0.04%.	

Note. AMSTAR = A Measurement Tool to Assess Systematic Reviews; CDS = Clinical Decision Support; EB = Evidenced Based; EHR = Electronic Health Record; HCP = Healthcare Providers; ICD = International Classification of Diseases; IQR = Interquartile Range; PDA = Personal Digital Assistant; RCTs = Randomized Controlled Trials; RX = Prescription; US = United States; VS = Versus.

APPENDIX B

JOB AID

FYI/ 3S-NSY requests

1. Add Bedside Procedure Row to Newborn Assessment Flowsheet above the NIPS pain scale group

Newborn Assessment		Skin/Wound/PU	LDA	IV/MAR	Newborn Surgical L
Vitals	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Mode: Accordion Expanded View All			
Apnea Monitor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			11/3/14	
Bedside Procedures/T...	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			1400	
NIPS (Neonatal/Infant ...	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Apnea Monitor			
Neonatal Abstinence S...	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Apnea Monitor			
ID and Safety	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Bedside Procedures/Tests			
Admission Documenta...	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Procedure/Test Done at			
Neuro	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NIPS (Neonatal/Infant Pain Scale)			
Skin	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Facial Expression			
Head and Neck	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cry			
Chest	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Breathing Patterns			
Cardiovascular	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Arms			
Abdomen	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Legs			
Card	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	State of Arousal			
Anus/Rectum	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NIPS Score			
GU	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pain Intervention			

2. Attach BPA to the Procedure Type Row in The Newborn surgical Log Flowsheet to remind staff to complete pain scores.

The screenshot shows the 'Newborn Surgical Log' interface. At the top, it displays '11/03/14 1500' and '1500'. Below this, there is a 'Procedure' section with a 'Select Single Option: (F5)' dropdown menu. The dropdown menu is open, showing options: 'Circumcision', 'Frenulectomy', 'Lumbar puncture', 'Tying of digit', 'Other (Comment)', and 'Comment: (F5)'. A blue icon representing a BPA (Best Practice Advisory) is attached to the 'Procedure' row.

The screenshot shows a 'Pain Documentation Alert' dialog box. The message reads: 'Complete Pain Score documentation for procedure (at start of procedure) and post procedure/intervention (30 min after procedure/intervention completed)'. Below the message is a text field for 'Acknowledge reason:' and an 'Action Taken' button. At the bottom of the dialog are 'Accept' and 'Cancel' buttons.

APPENDIX C

POWER POINT PRESENTATION:
DOCUMENTATION: PROCEDURAL PAIN MANAGEMENT

Procedural Pain Management

LAUREN FLOWERS MSN, RNC, ANM

Painful procedures

- Heel stick or heel lancing
- Circumcision
- Frenulectomy
- Lumbar puncture
- IV insertion
- Injections
- Fractured clavicles

Neonatal Pain Management

- Pain is defined as “an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage.” (International Association for the Study of Pain)
- Infants between the ages of 25-42 weeks gestation experience on average 14 painful procedures/day
- The most frequent procedure is the heel stick
- Evidence suggests that the cumulative effects of repeated painful medical procedures on the developing brain may pose harmful consequences later in life

Goal

- Assess and manage neonatal pain using validated pain scales
- Follow hospital guidelines & Policies and procedures to provide the knowledge necessary to effectively assess and manage procedural pain

NIPS

- Neonatal Infant Pain Scale (NIPS) is a behavioral scale tested for validity and reliability to be used on both full-term and pre-term infants.
 - 28-42 weeks gestation
 - The scale uses behaviors nurses describe as being indicative of pain or distress in newborns
- Composed of six (6) indicators
 - facial expression
 - cry
 - breathing patterns
 - arms
 - legs
 - state of arousal

Pain level Intervention

0-2 = mild pain	None
3-4 = mild to moderate	Non-pharmacological intervention with a reassessment in 30 minutes
> 4 = severe pain	Non-pharmacological intervention and possible pharmacological with a reassessment in 30 minutes

NIPS

NIPS (Neonatal/Infant Pain Scale)

Facial Expression	
Cry	
Breathing Patterns	
Arms	
Legs	
State of Arousal	
NIPS Score	
Pain Intervention	

NIPS (Neonatal/Infant Pain Scale)

Facial Expression		12	
Cry			
Breathing Patterns			
Arms			
Legs			
State of Arousal			
NIPS Score			
Pain Intervention			

Neonatal Abstinence Scoring System

 Is infant at risk of narcotic

ID and Safety

Band #

selection form

0=relaxed muscles
1=grimace

NIPS

NIPS (Neonatal/Infant Pain Scale)	
Facial Expression	
Cry	1/2
Breathing Patterns	
Arms	
Legs	
State of Arousal	
NIPS Score	
Pain Intervention	
Neonatal Abstinence Scoring System	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Is infant at risk of narcotic	
ID and Safety	
Band #	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ID Verified	

Selection Form X
 0=no cry
 1=whimper
 2=vigorous cry
 Accept Cancel

NIPS (Neonatal/Infant Pain Scale)	
Facial Expression	
Cry	
Breathing Patterns	
Arms	1/2
Legs	
State of Arousal	
NIPS Score	
Pain Intervention	
Neonatal Abstinence Scoring System	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Is infant at risk of narcotic	
ID and Safety	
Band #	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ID Verified	
Verified With	
Identification	

Selection Form X
 0=relaxed/restrained
 1=flexed/extended
 Accept Cancel

NIPS (Neonatal/Infant Pain Scale)	
Facial Expression	
Cry	
Breathing Patterns	
Arms	
Legs	
State of Arousal	
NIPS Score	
Pain Intervention	
Neonatal Abstinence Scoring System	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Is infant at risk of narcotic	
ID and Safety	
Band #	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ID Verified	
Verified With	
Identification	
Safety	

Selection Form X
 0=relaxed
 1=change in breathing
 Accept Cancel

NIPS (Neonatal/Infant Pain Scale)	
Facial Expression	
Cry	
Breathing Patterns	
Arms	
Legs	1/2
State of Arousal	
NIPS Score	
Pain Intervention	
Neonatal Abstinence Scoring System	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Is infant at risk of narcotic	
ID and Safety	
Band #	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ID Verified	
Verified With	
Identification	
Safety	

Selection Form X
 0=relaxed/restrained
 1=flexed/extended
 Accept Cancel

NIPS

NIPS (Neonatal/Infant Pain Scale)

Facial Expression			
Cry			
Breathing Pattern			
Arms			
Legs			
State of Arousal			
NIPS Score			
Pain Intervention			

Neonatal Abstinence Scoring System

Is infant at risk of narcotic

ID and Safety

Band #	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ID Verified	
Verified With	
Identification	
Safety	
Security Alarm Tag #	

11/24/14 1040

Pain Intervention

Select Multiple Options: (F5)

- None
- Swaddled
- Held
- Being Fed
- Audio Distract.
- Tactile Distract.
- Pacifier
- Sucrose Pacifier
- Reposition
- Facilitated Tuck
- Blanket Roll
- Analgesia
- Other (Comment)

NIPS (Neonatal/Infant Pain Scale)

Facial Expression			
Cry			
Breathing Pattern			
Arms			
Legs			
State of Arousal			
NIPS Score			
Pain Intervention			

Neonatal Abstinence Scoring System

Is infant at risk of narcotic

ID and Safety

Band #	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ID Verified	
Verified With	
Identification	
Safety	
Security Alarm Tag #	
Disposition of Patient	Nursery
Observation Status	

11/24/14 1040

Pain Intervention

Select Multiple Options: (F5)

- None
- Swaddled
- Held
- Being Fed
- Audio Distract.
- Tactile Distract.
- Pacifier
- Sucrose Pacifier
- Reposition
- Facilitated Tuck
- Blanket Roll
- Analgesia
- Other (Comment)

Current Practice

Doc Dashboard

Newborn Assessment
 Skin/Wound/PU
 LDA
 N/MAI
 Newborn Surgical Log
 Patient Profile

Module	Value	Unit	Color
Wtals	1025/4		Green
Neonatal Abstinence S.	2247	00%	Green

Make/ Accurate / Expanded

Module	Value	Unit	Color
Temp			Green
Temp int			Green
Pulse			Green
Resp			Green
SpO2			Green
SpO2 Mean			Green
SpO2 Location			Green
SpO2 Probe Location			Green
Oxygen Delivery Device			Green
FIO2 (%) Set			Green
EtOxygen Start/Off			Green
O2 Flow Rate (l/min)			Green
Height			Green
Weight			Green
Doing Weight			Green
Head Cx			Green
Chest Circumference (cm)			Green
Umbilic			Green
Apnea Monitor			Green
Apnea Monitor			Green
NPS (Neonatal Infant Pain Scale)			Green
Facial Expression			Green
Cry			Green
Breathing Patterns			Green
Arms			Green
Legs			Green
State of Arousal			Green
NPS Score			Green
Pain Intervention			Green

Neonatal Abstinence Scoring System

NPs currently found under the Newborn Assessment

Nurses

- play an essential role in optimizing pain assessment and management
- are in key positions to observe an infants response to painful procedures
- are patient advocates
- should always practice with evidenced based practice

END

• Questions